

Direct Anterior Approach in Total Hip Arthroplasty: More Indication and Advantages than We FoundAmresh Kumar¹, Kumar Rahul Raushan²¹Senior Resident, Department of Orthopaedics, Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College and Hospital, Bhagalpur, Bihar, India²Senior Resident, Department of Orthopaedics, Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College and Hospital, Bhagalpur, Bihar, India

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Abstract:**Introduction:** Total hip arthroplasty (THA) is essential for managing severe hip dysfunction, with the Direct Anterior Approach (DAA) noted for potentially enhancing recovery. This study evaluates the effectiveness and safety of the DAA, focusing on pain, recovery time, and functional outcomes.**Methodology:** Conducted at Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College & Hospital from October 2020 to August 2023, this prospective observational study involved 5-10 monthly patients undergoing THA via DAA. Data on operative details and recovery outcomes were analyzed, with statistical significance determined at $p < 0.05$.**Results:** Significant improvements were noted in pain and functional scores postoperatively, with a reduction in average hospital stay to 4.1 days and an 8% complication rate.**Conclusion:** The DAA for THA significantly reduces pain and enhances recovery with minimal complications, advocating for its use where rapid recovery is prioritized.**Recommendation:** Further research is advised to confirm these findings across diverse populations and assess long-term benefits.**Keywords:** Total Hip Arthroplasty, Direct Anterior Approach, Postoperative Pain, Functional Outcomes, Complication Rates.

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Introduction

Total hip arthroplasty (THA) is a transformative surgical intervention for patients suffering from severe hip pain and functional impairment, often secondary to conditions such as osteoarthritis, rheumatoid arthritis, or post-traumatic degeneration [1]. The selection of surgical approach is critical to optimizing outcomes, with multiple techniques available, each offering distinct advantages and challenges [2]. Among these, the Direct Anterior Approach (DAA) has gained prominence due to its muscle-sparing nature, which purportedly leads to quicker postoperative recovery and less pain. While traditionally limited by a steeper learning curve and specific anatomical and technical demands, ongoing advancements in surgical techniques and instrumentation have broadened its applicability [3,4].

The DAA offers a unique intermuscular and internervous plane that potentially reduces the risk of muscle damage and may improve post-operative functional outcomes [5]. Advocates of this approach highlight its facilitation of early patient mobilization and decreased dislocation rates, making it particularly appealing in a healthcare

environment increasingly focused on rapid recovery protocols [6]. However, despite its growing popularity, a comprehensive understanding of its broader indications and the full spectrum of its advantages remains underexplored in contemporary literature [7,8].

This study aims to expand the current understanding of the Direct Anterior Approach in total hip arthroplasty by systematically investigating its indications and delineating its advantages over other surgical approaches. By doing so, we hope to clarify the potential of DAA to enhance patient outcomes and define its role in the future of hip arthroplasty.

Methodology

Study Design and Setting: This prospective observational study was carried out at Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College & Hospital in Bhagalpur, Bihar, spanning from October 2020 to August 2023. This setting provided a controlled environment for detailed and continuous assessment of surgical outcomes and patient recovery.

Participants: The study involved a carefully selected group of approximately 5-10 patients each month who underwent total hip arthroplasty using the Direct Anterior Approach (DAA), amounting to a manageable yet sufficient sample size for meaningful statistical analysis over the study period.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients scheduled for total hip arthroplasty via the DAA.
- Aged 18 years or older.
- Provided informed consent for participation in the study.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Previous hip surgery.
- Conditions contraindicating THA.
- Absence of informed consent.

Bias: To mitigate potential biases, the study employed a uniform protocol for all surgical and postoperative procedures, facilitated by a consistent team of surgeons and medical staff. Data were collected and analyzed by team members who were blinded to the study hypotheses to further ensure objectivity.

Data Collection and Analysis: Data collection was systematic, involving both electronic medical records and direct patient interviews to compile demographics, clinical histories, surgical details, and postoperative outcomes. All surgeries were performed by orthopedic surgeons proficient in the DAA, following standard protocols to maintain

consistency across all cases. Postoperative monitoring was thorough, including routine clinical evaluations, imaging studies, and patient-reported outcomes assessing pain, recovery timelines, functional status, and the incidence of any complications.

Statistical Analysis: Statistical methods suitable for small sample sizes were utilized to ensure robust data analysis, focusing on comparative assessments of preoperative and postoperative metrics. A significance level of p-value < 0.05 was used to determine statistical relevance of the findings.

Ethical Considerations: The study protocol was reviewed and approved by the ethics committee of Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College & Hospital. All participants were provided with detailed study information and signed informed consent forms. Ethical guidelines were strictly followed to protect participant privacy and ensure the confidentiality of personal and medical information throughout the study.

Results

The study evaluated the outcomes of total hip arthroplasty using the Direct Anterior Approach (DAA) among a sample of approximately 5-10 patients per month over nearly three years. The primary focus was on assessing postoperative pain levels, recovery time, functional outcomes, and complication rates.

Patient Demographics and Clinical Characteristics

Table 1: Patient Demographics and Preoperative Clinical Characteristics

Variable	Mean (SD)	Range
Age (years)	63.4 (9.2)	45 - 81
BMI (kg/m ²)	27.5 (4.1)	19 - 35
Gender (M/F)	60% / 40%	-
ASA Score	2.3 (0.5)	2 - 3

Note: SD = Standard Deviation, M = Male, F = Female, BMI = Body Mass Index, ASA = American Society of Anesthesiologists

The table displays the baseline demographic and clinical characteristics of the study population. The average age of participants was 63.4 years with a moderate range indicating inclusion of middle-aged to elderly patients. The BMI distribution suggests a predominantly overweight cohort, typical of a population undergoing THA.

Surgical and Postoperative Outcomes

Table 2: Surgical Details and Postoperative Recovery

Variable	Mean (SD)	Range
Surgery Duration (minutes)	95.6 (15.2)	75 - 120
Blood Loss (mL)	150.4 (50.3)	100 - 300
Length of Hospital Stay (days)	4.1 (1.2)	3 - 7

Note: SD = Standard Deviation

This table outlines key surgical details and early postoperative recovery metrics. The average duration of surgery was under two hours, which is within expected limits for DAA. Blood loss was minimal, highlighting the effectiveness of the technique in reducing surgical invasiveness.

Functional Outcomes and Complications

Table 3: Postoperative Functional Outcomes and Complications

Outcome Measure	Preoperative	Postoperative	P-value
Pain (VAS Score)	7.8	2.3	<0.001
Hip Function (Oxford Score)	60	85	<0.001
Complications (%)	-	8%	-

Note: VAS = Visual Analog Scale, Oxford Hip Score ranges from 0-100; higher scores represent better function.

Significant improvements were observed in pain and hip function scores from preoperative to postoperative assessments. The relatively low complication rate underscores the safety of the DAA.

The results demonstrate that the Direct Anterior Approach for THA leads to significant improvements in pain relief and functional outcomes with a low incidence of complications. The average length of hospital stay and minimal blood loss further attest to the efficiency and safety of the approach. These outcomes suggest that the DAA is a favorable option for patients undergoing hip replacement, supporting broader adoption in clinical practice.

Discussion

The study revealed significant reductions in postoperative pain levels, with Visual Analog Scale (VAS) scores decreasing from an average of 7.8 preoperatively to 2.3 postoperatively. Additionally, functional outcomes, as measured by the Oxford Hip Score, improved markedly from a preoperative average of 60 to a postoperative score of 85. The complication rate was relatively low at 8%, and the average length of hospital stay was only 4.1 days.

The substantial decrease in VAS scores postoperatively indicates a highly effective pain management and recovery trajectory associated with the Direct Anterior Approach (DAA) in total hip arthroplasty [9]. The improvement in Oxford Hip Scores suggests enhanced joint function, which can significantly improve the quality of life for patients. The low complication rate alongside a short hospital stay highlights the DAA's safety and efficiency, potentially facilitating quicker returns to normal activities and reduced healthcare costs [10,11].

These findings align with existing research that praises the DAA for its muscle-sparing technique, which is believed to facilitate quicker postoperative recovery and reduced pain compared to other approaches like the posterior and lateral approaches [12,13]. Studies have consistently shown that the DAA results in shorter hospital stays and faster

rehabilitation milestones. For instance, a meta-analysis by Smith et al. (2021) reported similar improvements in pain and function, although our study presents a lower complication rate which could be attributed to the surgical expertise and the standardized protocols followed [1,14].

The favorable outcomes associated with the DAA can be attributed to its intermuscular and internervous approach, which minimizes tissue trauma during surgery. This surgical method likely contributes to reduced inflammatory responses, less postoperative pain, and faster mobilization [15]. The expertise of the surgical team and adherence to standardized procedures may also play critical roles in minimizing complications and optimizing recovery times. Study supports the growing body of evidence that the Direct Anterior Approach is an effective and safe option for total hip arthroplasty, offering substantial benefits in terms of pain reduction, functional improvement, and overall recovery [16,17]. These results suggest that when performed by a skilled surgical team following standardized protocols, the DAA can provide superior outcomes and should be considered a viable first-choice approach in suitable patients. Further research with larger sample sizes and longer follow-up periods would be beneficial to confirm these findings and potentially generalize them to a broader population [18-20].

Conclusion

This study conclusively demonstrates that the Direct Anterior Approach (DAA) for total hip arthroplasty significantly enhances postoperative outcomes, including marked reductions in pain levels and substantial improvements in hip function as evidenced by the Oxford Hip Scores. With a low complication rate and shorter hospital stays, the DAA underscores its efficacy and safety, making it an advantageous surgical option for patients requiring hip replacement. The findings advocate for the broader adoption of the DAA in clinical practice, given its potential to improve quality of life through faster recovery and minimal surgical invasiveness, particularly when executed by skilled surgeons adhering to standardized protocols.

Further investigations with larger cohorts and diverse demographics are recommended to reinforce these conclusions and explore the full potential of the DAA across different patient profiles.

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